

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Kinoti****FIRST NAME: Meme****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: One (1)****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show essential information below:

The author applied XUS conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author x did use Zotero to insert references

The author x did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Quotation Marks (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)
3. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 11-23)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56-60)

A REVIEW OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND WRITING TOOLS

1) INTRODUCTION

For this course, I reviewed important writing guidelines, including text formatting, spelling using the US spelling and punctuation placement rules, and general referencing conventions in academic writing. I also reviewed different other rules of style and their use in academic writing. I accessed and studied the following documents and videos.

- The EUCLID ACA-401D coursepack
- Imbedded course videos on academic research and writing
- A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations (Turabian)
- The Blue Book
- Sample doctoral dissertations
- I also reviewed the provided Zotero training videos and downloaded and installed the program on my computer

Studying these materials helped me review important research and writing guidelines that support academic studies at the Euclid University. The key activities that were most informative included 1) the use of a specific writing style guide, 2) proper use of the mechanics of style, 3) formal academic paper writing and formatting, 4) access and use for academic writing templates, and 5) the review of dissertation examples.

2) LESSONS LEARNED

Overall, this study introduced me to academic studies and writing essentials, including key rules of style. Part of this process was familiarizing myself with the preferable writing style guides for academic programs at EUCLID. I have used the writing style guides before, especially the American Psychological Association writing style guide and the 15th edition of Chicago Manual of Style. I have also worked within institutions that used the MLA and are consequently familiar with that as well. This was the first time though to utilize Chicago Manual of Style.

Other important activities for this course included downloading and reviewing templates for writing at Euclid, creating a quiz, and writing this response paper based on the study materials. All these activities took longer than I had anticipated, primarily because I am coming back to be a student after many years' absence. However, this is a good starting point for re-engaging in an academic pursuit for a degree, I consider essential for my personal development.

Above, I have listed the seven key concepts that I found helpful in studying the coursepack. Below I discuss each of these concepts as they relate to my studies.

a) The Basics of Essay Writing

Writing is about communicating. That is why the writing basics are essential as a guide for developing and setting out a good essay. I especially like the necessary steps outlined in an excellent essay writing process (EUCLID 2019, 1). Although these are proposed as guidelines and not as strict requirements, it has been my experience that the closer one follows many of these, the better the product, i.e., an essay that communicates well. Unfortunately, not following many of these can lead to poor writing that does not communicate as one would like it to.

Part of communicating has a clear message to share. That is where researching a topic fits in the writing process. I like to start my research as the author suggests, by asking critical questions about what I know about the subject and what else I need to research (EUCLID 2019, 2). To start the process, if not provided, I write out questions that I am interested in studying in line with my topic. I then challenge myself to write as much as I can on the subject from what I already know or think about the topic. This process helps me begin the writing and highlight gaps and information I need to find to complete my essay. Of course, these gaps change because as I take the next step, reading or interviewing sources about a topic, I find more gaps that I need to fill in. These form my basis for the

research and drafting of my essay. Once I have a finished draft, I either share it with others or just let it "sit" for a while. I revisit it once I have further information or corrections suggested to me by others who might have read the piece. I also incorporate other materials that I may have gathered or thought about during the rest period.

The above is also why I like that there is a focus on essay writing as a non-linear process with editing, redrafting, and having others helping in reading and correcting the essay. This is a critical process to developing a winning essay. A professor that I had for my graduate studies in the early 2000 used to say that no one wrote well, but we all rewrote better. This is an experience I have had in my many years of schooling and now as a faculty. Indeed, most people find writing to be an arduous task. I sure do. However, when I revisit material I drafted or wrote before and revised or rewrote them, the final product comes out much better. That is why I am comfortable sharing whatever I write with others to help me improve on them. Hence, corrections, revisions, and rewrites are part of my writing process and many others who embark on developing essays or any other written materials.

b) Plagiarism

Knowledge is iterative and builds on what already exists. That means we all build on what already exists either in writing or information communicated to us by others. Knowing when and how to use other people's ideas and to appropriately acknowledge through accurate citation is an essential part of developing one's own writing. It is even more important in academic settings since, by its very nature, academic writing depends on other sources for research and crafting written responses. Doing so inherently comes with the intentional or unintentional dangers for passing on information from whatever sources without proper acknowledgment or attribution. This does not have to be the case if one understands the appropriate ways to cite and for what reason.

Unfortunately, it is common knowledge that plagiarism has been on the ubiquitous rise of written material and especially with easy access to online content. The advent of social media and other information-sharing tools make casual passing on of information as one's own a more common problem. In writing, word-processing tools that make cut and paste easy also make plagiarism possible in ways that would not have been likely half a century ago. Given the above, there is growing confusion about what constitutes plagiarism. That is why I appreciated the short but concise definition of plagiarism as "... when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information" (EUCLID 2019, 5). I like this definition because it captures the essence of plagiarism as the passing of information as one's contribution when it is borrowed from a source without proper attribution.

Plagiarism is wrong on so many levels, not the least of which is fraudulent and unethical (EUCLID 2019, 5). Apart from these otherwise severe reasons not to pass on others information as one, plagiarism is laziness and unacademic. It is unfair to the rigor of academic exercise to lift materials and not lay out how and where one learned the information. Indeed, I would argue that this is not an exercise that one would take lightly

if they take the learning enterprise seriously. It is thievery and, in some cases, has significant loss to those whose ideas are stolen.

Apart from thievery from the authors' hard work and potential loss, plagiarism can also have significant repercussions, including loss of one's reputation, loss of credentials, and sometimes loss of a job. In the last decade, there have been several publicly significant fallouts due to plagiarism, including the German Education and Defense ministers' resignation both over their plagiarized works for their university theses (*BBC News Online* 2011; *DW News Online* 2013). Others include Brian Swart, a Professor of Economics who was forced to resign for plagiarizing parts of his dissertation (Sullivan 2013); Fr. Thomas Rosica, CSB, forced to resign as CEO of the Salt and Light Media Foundation for plagiarizing several of his speeches and op-eds (*The Catholic World Report* 2019); and the current US president-elect Joe Biden who was forced to drop out of the bid for the presidency in 1988 due to accusations of plagiarism (Waxman 2019).

c) Literature Review

As indicated above, academic writing is about synthesizing sources with personal arguments to support learning. These sources form a significant of the knowledge one gleans through the process. I like the 11 reminders under this section because they summarize essential information that I need in my studies. I am saving this document to return to often throughout my studies at EUCLID.

This section also highlights the processes for correctly accessing and using materials other than one's arguments. It also lays out proper writing conventions, including commas, quotation marks, and periods. These conventions, many of which can be confusing, help one layout their arguments that support a good flow of ideas - which aids in better communication (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)

d) American Versus British English

English is my fourth language and, therefore, not the most natural to me. Additionally, my earlier schooling was in UK English, while my graduate studies have been in US English. Navigating these differences has been a long-term learning experiment for me. I am glad that for my studies at Euclid, I can choose what format to use. I will stick with US English for my reviews because that is what I use in my current job and are likely to make fewer mistakes when writing.

e) Chicago Manual of Style

Every academic discipline and, therefore, training institutions seek to embody professional development that is credible and verifiable. Part of that process is to have standardized communication processes, including having agreed-upon writing styles that define that profession. A good case for this is the legal profession. Therefore, law schools need an agreed professional writing guide that helps standardize both the writing and the

communication within the discipline. This is where the Blue Book fits as a tool for harmonizing the representation of ideas and communication.

Standardization of communication is impossible without an agreed-upon mechanics of style for writing - for both academic and professional communication materials. It is essential to learn the basic mechanics of style as applied within a particular profession if it is the primary communication format. This might be different from what is demanded in the academic setting. However, both are important as the training within an educational environment ought to prepare one for the professional fields within the discipline.

In my experience as a student as well as a teacher, good writing follows some basic rules of the game and which are not possible without following a pre-determined format. Many students resist the use of a specific academic writing guide, arguing that this will not be required of them in an employment setting - or their career goal. However, my response to them is that developing a habit of good writing, which a specific writing guide imposes on one's writing, is essential, if for nothing else, as training in developing a practice to write well. This guides my appreciation for understanding and using proper academic paper writing and formatting.

f) Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

English, being a growing and dynamic form of communication, borrows generously from other languages, existing and some defunct. In its development as a language, English especially borrowed extensively from other Proto-Indo-European languages (Criado-Pena 2019). This is true for words borrowed out of Latin, with some estimates of 65% of all English words having Latin roots (Eskenazi 2000). Some of these words are sometimes represented by standard abbreviations and expressions that carry specific agreed on meanings within different disciplines. these are useful for readily communicating important information.

The legal profession utilizes many Latin abbreviations and expressions. Given that my studies are within this discipline, I hope to study these and be familiar with their usage. It was, therefore, useful for me to see the most common of these abbreviations summarized here.

3) CONCLUSION

Every study institution tries to develop tools and supports for students that they need to use in their education process. Euclid is no different in developing writing requirements and templates that students need to use. This study helped me review essential materials foundational to academic writing and my studies at Euclid. Downloading and saving these was a good step towards preparing myself for the next few years of study.

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